

Integración de tecnologías sub-THz/THz en testbed

Document versión. V1.1

30/10/2024

**Programa de Universalización de Infraestructuras
Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G I+D**

Fundació Privada i2CAT
Internet i Innovació Digital a Catalunya
C/ Gran Capità 2-4, Edifici Nexus I
2a planta, 08034 Barcelona

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	XX
Líder del PT	XX
Editor Principal	José Joaquín Escudero Garzás
Contribuyentes	Pablo González Méndez, Pablo Vilar Gómez, María Purriños Paz,
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

PU	Público
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento

Versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
V1	Gradient		20/10/2024	Cambio de formato
V1.1	Gradient		30/10/2024	Resultados finales

Content

01. Introduction and scope	6
02. Complete system	6
03. Communications test plan and results	9
3.1 Software communications test plan and results	9
3.2 Hardware communication test plan and results.....	12
04. Sensing test plan and results	16
05. Platform validation - Sensing and Communications	20
5.1 FPGA analysis	21
5.2 BER measurement	22
Conclusions and future work.....	23

Figure List

Figure 1: Simplified block diagram of the hardware setup.	7
Figure 2: Assembly for data communication over sub-THz	7
Figure 3: Modulator test output.....	10
Figure 4: Comparison of Vivado and expected outputs.	11
Figure 5: Expected and received 16QAM constellations.	11
Figure 6: Channel estimation.	12
Figure 7: Loopback between TX and RX on the hardware platform.....	13
Figure 8: Equalised IQ symbols on reception.....	13
Figure 9: Channel estimation on reception	13
Figure 10: Time comparison of IQ symbols transmitted and received.....	14
Figure 11: IQ symbols received in the first stream	15
Figure 12: IQ symbols received in the second stream	15
Figure 13: IQ symbols received in the third stream	15
Figure 14: IQ symbols received in the fourth stream	15
Figure 15: MER measured in the first stream	16
Figure 16: MER measured in the second stream.....	16
Figure 17: MER measured in the third stream.....	16
Figure 18: MER measured in the fourth stream	16
Figure 19 Range-Doppler with static target at 1m.....	17
Figure 20 Range-Time with static target at 1m.....	17
Figure 21 Metallic target at 4.32m.....	18
Figure 22 Human target moving farther and closer to the system	18
Figure 23 Range-Doppler plot with a pillar at 3m and a metallic box at 4.3m.....	18
Figure 24 Human target at 1m and metallic box at 1.84m	18
Figure 25 Multitarget test setups	19
Figure 26 Breathing test setup	19
Figure 27 Phase-Slow Time plot	19
Figure 28 Moving target setup	20
Figure 29 Range-Slow Time plot	20
Figure 30 Wooden target at 1m	20
Figure 31: Resource analysis.	21
Figure 32: Timing analysis.....	21
Figure 33: Simplified diagram of the blocks involved in the BER calculation	22

Table List

Table 1: Project KPIs - Target and achived values.....	6
Table 2: Software communications test battery.....	10
Table 3: Hardware communications test battery.	12
Table 4: Sensing test battery.	17
Table 5: BER results in the four 400 MHz bands measured at different distances:.....	23

01. Introduction and scope

This document describes the integration of the sub-THz/THz technologies described in the D3.2 deliverable. The objective of this task is to test the communications link and integrated sensing. This integration is carried out in the form of a point-to-point radio link that includes the hardware equipment presented in D3.2 on which the physical layer is implemented. In addition, it will be possible to change the operating mode of the prototype to physical space sensing mode and detect targets. This report includes the measures, at the functional and performance level, that validate the performance of the sub-THz/THz technologies selected in the testbed. In this sense, the document will include the values of the KPIs defined in D3.2 measured on the testbed.

The following table shows the target KPIs and the values accomplished through the validation plan. All target KPIs are above the threshold, and notably the data rate and the detection range largely exceed the reference values. The system is also capable of identifying target speed for slow movement. Due to hardware restrictions, motivated by budget constraints, the range resolution is below the reference value because the achievement of this objective would have compromised other KPIs such as the detection range. Therefore, this impairment can be solved with high-performance processing components. Besides, given the short distance inherent to sub-THz links, we consider it more relevant to comply with the other sensing parameters when establishing a tradeoff between the KPIs.

KPI	Target value	Achieved value
Carrier frequency	Higher than 90 GHz	91.525 GHz
Bandwidth	Larger than 1,5 GHz	1.6 GHz
Link data rate	Larger than 2 Gbps (L1-L2)	3.856 Gbps (L1)
Detection range of moving targets	1 m	Up to 4 m
Range resolution	10 cm	37.5 cm
Identification of object getting close / away	Yes	Yes
Target speed	N/A	Pedestrian and person breathing

Table 1: Project KPIs - Target and achieved values

02. Complete system

This section describes the final hardware assembly used for the transmission and reception in the sub-THz band of the waveform designed for simultaneous sensing and communication, referred

to as ISAC (Integrated Sensing and Communication). The high-level block diagram of the system is shown in Figure 1, in addition, Figure 2 presents an image of the assembly highlighting its various components. For the sake of completeness, a very detailed explanation of the different elements presented in the complete system is provide in the previous deliverable *D3.2 Diseño y evaluación final de tecnologías sub-THz/THz de 6G para servicios XR*.

Figure 1: Simplified block diagram of the hardware setup.

Figure 2: Assembly for data communication over sub-THz

The complete system consists of two distinguishable elements: the ZCU208 platform, which integrates an RFSoc-type FPGA, and a radio frequency front-end. These elements are identified in Figure 2.

Following the communication flow, four signal streams are generated by the ISAC waveform transmitter and converted to the analogue domain by the DACs integrated in the RFSoc. Each of these streams has a bandwidth of 400 MHz and focus on contiguous frequencies across the spectrum. Therefore, in the intermediate frequency (IF) transmission chain, the four frequency components are merged into a single stream, resulting in the 1.6 GHz bandwidth transmission waveform. It is this "single" signal that feeds the sub-THz converter and is therefore transmitted through the sub-THz channel, centred at $f_c = 91.525$ GHz.

At the receiver, the reverse of the transmission process is performed, i.e. the signal is received via the sub-THz front-end where the complete signal is downlinked to an IF band. The chain of this band in turn divides and filters the four original 400 MHz BW streams that digitise through the ADCs integrated in the RFSoc.

Finally, the ISAC waveform receiver retrieves the transmitted data for communication as well as the radar signal for further processing.

To achieve the value presented in KPI#3 a redesign of the LDPC code rate was necessary, the new value being $r = \frac{11}{14}$. In this way, the bitrate R value corresponding to one of the streams can be obtained by design according to the following formula:

$$R \text{ (Mbits/s)} = \frac{N_{ploadSymb} \times N_{bitsOFDMsymb} \times r}{N_{totalSymb} \times \left(\frac{N_{FFT}}{2} + CP\right) \times T_{CLK}} = \frac{24 \times 3328 \times \frac{11}{14}}{25 \times (512 + 128) \times \frac{1}{245.76 \text{ MHz}}} = 963.94 \text{ Mbits/s}$$

where:

- $N_{ploadSymb}$: OFDM payload symbols per frame (24)
- $N_{bitsOFDMsymb}$: Total bits in OFDM symbol (3328)
- r : LDPC Rate (11/14)
- $N_{totalSymb}$: Total OFDM symbols per frame (25)
- N_{FFT} : Number of subcarriers per OFDM symbol (1024)
- CP : Cyclic Prefix length (256)
- T_{CLK} : FPGA clock period ($\frac{1}{245.76 \text{ MHz}}$)

To obtain the bitrate of the entire system, simply quadruple this value, giving a total bitrate set by design of: $R_t = 3.856 \text{ Gbits/s}$.

03. Communications test plan and results

This section describes the test plan performed to verify the correct operation of the complete communications system, both at the software and hardware levels. The main objective of these tests is to verify that the system operates according to the expected specifications. The tests were carried out in two main phases:

1. **Waveform verification and validation:** Vitis Model Composer (VMC) was used to perform unit tests on each block that integrates the system, as well as on the OFDM modulator and OFDM demodulator chains. This ensures that the individual blocks function correctly both in isolation and within the integrated system. In addition, Vitis Model Composer allows the implementation of fixed-point and floating-point blocks, which makes it possible to implement signal processing blocks within the quantization limitations of the hardware. To verify its correct operation, a cross simulation was performed between the model developed in Matlab and its quantized version in Vitis Model Composer. Through asserts, possible discrepancies and errors were evaluated, thus ensuring coherence between both implementations.
2. **Hardware verification and validation:** the system was implemented in the RFSoc ZCU208 and the results obtained were verified with the simulations performed in Matlab, whose characteristics are explained in deliverable D3.2. This process ensures that the behaviour in hardware was aligned with the simulations, thus guaranteeing an adequate transition between the simulation environment and the hardware deployment.

It is important to highlight that, during these tests, the LDPC encoding/decoding process has not been included, in order to directly evaluate the performance over an ideal channel and verify that the IQ symbols are transmitted and received correctly without the influence of error correction.

3.1 Software communications test plan and results

To validate the correct operation of the OFDM modulation and demodulation chains, a set of tests have been performed following the developed test plan. This section will detail the objectives and results of these tests.

Test name	Objective
Unit tests	Verify, individually, all the blocks that compose the OFDM modulator and demodulator.
OFDM modulator test	Verify the correct operation of OFDM modulation using the waveform configuration simulated in Matlab.

OFDM demodulator test

Verify the correct operation of OFDM demodulation using an ideal channel, with a WF simulated in Matlab.

Table 2: Software communications test battery.

The first tests performed corresponded to the unit tests, being the purpose to validate the correct operation of each of the system blocks individually. For this purpose, the ideal results, previously calculated in Matlab, were compared with those generated by Vitis Model Composer. This is done by means of asserts, as mentioned above.

As an example, the modulator block, whose function is to convert the input bits into OFDM symbols, is presented. The results obtained are shown in Figure 3, where it is evident that the data generated by the modulator in Vitis coincides exactly with the theoretical results in Matlab. This correspondence confirms that the OFDM modulator implementation meets the established specifications.

Figure 3: Modulator test output

The second test performed corresponds to the complete OFDM modulation chain. The objective of this test is to verify that the implementation developed in Vitis Model Composer, to be later implemented in Vivado, works according to the established specifications. The following figures show that the simulated results coincide with the expected results, thus confirming the correct implementation of the system.

Figure 4: Comparison of Vivado and expected outputs.

Finally, the third test focuses on the OFDM demodulation. In this test, both OFDM modulation and an ideal channel are implemented, followed by demodulation. The objective is to recover at the demodulation output the same symbols that were sent from the transmitter (TX), using an ideal channel, which in this case introduces delays in the data. With an ideal, noise-free channel, the constellation obtained matches the expected one, and the channel estimation remains flat, as anticipated. The following images display both the expected and received constellations, as well as the flat channel estimation, verifying that the results are as expected. This confirms that the demodulation implementation works correctly.

Figure 5: Expected and received 16QAM constellations.

Figure 6: Channel estimation.

3.2 Hardware communication test plan and results

To validate the correct operation of the hardware dedicated to communications, a test plan has been developed. This section will detail the objectives and results of these tests.

Test Name	Channel	TX signal bandwidth	Objective
Data communication on RFSoc	SMA cable	400 MHz	Verify the correct operation of the blocks developed in VMC on the hardware platform
Full bandwidth data communication on RFSoc	Sub-THz	1.6 GHz	Verify correct signal reception through the sub-THz channel.

Table 3: Hardware communications test battery.

For this test, a loopback is performed between the transmitter and the ISAC receiver on only one of the 400 MHz bandwidth streams to verify the correct recovery of the transmitted IQ symbols. A channel as simple as possible is chosen, so an SMA cable is used directly. The advantage of this

is that it works under favourable conditions, where an error correcting block (LDPC) should not be necessary.

Figure 7: Loopback between TX and RX on the hardware platform

In Figure 8 and Figure 9, we show the IQ symbols recovered after equalization, the channel estimation.

Figure 8: Equalised IQ symbols on reception

Figure 9: Channel estimation on reception

It is also verified that the order of the received symbols coincides with the order of the transmitted symbols. The Figure 10 shows (in red) the IQ symbols sent and the IQ symbols received (in blue); it can be seen that the order is maintained since both graphs are approximately superimposed.

Figure 10: Time comparison of IQ symbols transmitted and received

The next test aims to verify the correct reception of the complete signal, i.e. 4 streams of 400 MHz each, when transmitted through the sub-THz channel. Thus, during this test, the setup illustrated in Figure 1 is used, with a distance between the transmitter and receiver of about 60 cm. Since it is not an ideal channel, during this test we can already observe how noise affects the quality of the received signal.

Figure 11, Figure 12, Figure 13 and Figure 14 show the received signal constellations of each of the streams compared to the transmitted IQ constellation marked as the red dots centred in the point clouds.

Figure 11: IQ symbols received in the first stream

Figure 12: IQ symbols received in the second stream

Figure 13: IQ symbols received in the third stream

Figure 14: IQ symbols received in the fourth stream

Figure 15, Figure 16, Figure 17 and Figure 18 show the measured MER (Modulation Error Ratio) of each of the signal streams. In this scenario, the MER is a measure analogous to the signal to noise ratio. It represents the received signal level versus the system noise level, expressed in dB, and is defined by the following equation:

$$MER(dB) = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\sum |I_n + Q_n|^2}{\sum |(I_n + Q_n) - (\tilde{I}_n + \tilde{Q}_n)|^2} \right)$$

Where:

- $(I_n + Q_n)$ is the vector representing the symbol being measured at index n .
- $(\tilde{I}_n + \tilde{Q}_n)$ is the ideal vector close to the actual symbol being measured.

Figure 15: MER measured in the first stream

Figure 16: MER measured in the second stream

Figure 17: MER measured in the third stream

Figure 18: MER measured in the fourth stream

It can be observed how the MER falls in the fourth stream, being this result consistent with Figure 14, where a higher dispersion of the received IQ symbols can be seen.

04. Sensing test plan and results

In order to evaluate the system's sensing capabilities and characteristics a test plan has been prepared. In this section, the tests are outlined along with explanations of their implementation and purpose.

Test name	Target	Distance	Plot	Objective
Short distance	Metallic static	<1.5m	Range-Doppler	Verify basic sensing capabilities
Long distance	Static	>1,5m	Range-Doppler	Determine maximum sensing range

Multiple targets	Static	1m-5m	Range-Doppler	Confirm range resolution
Breathing	Human static	<1.5m	Range-Doppler	Breathing
Movement	Moving human	1m-5m	Range-Slow time	Verify capabilities to detect moving targets
Different radar cross section	Static	<1.5m	Range-Doppler	Testing how well other materials reflect the sub-THz signal

Table 4: Sensing test battery.

The first test to be performed consists of short distance detection using a flat metallic object as the target. The purpose of the test is to verify the basic sensing capabilities; in this case confirming if the target is visible in the Range-Doppler plot and if the estimated range is correct. From the first measurement the signal delay caused by the system itself is obtained; this information is taken into consideration for the target range estimation. After that, the test should be repeated multiple times to confirm the signal delay caused by the system is not variable, which would make the range estimation unreliable.

Figure 19 Range-Doppler with static target at 1m

Figure 20 Range-Time with static target at 1m

After the system delay was determined, the following test accurately showed the target distance. The test was repeated 5 times to confirm that the system delay is not variable.

Once the basic sensing is confirmed to be operational, the following tests are performed to verify the maximum range and range resolution. For the maximum range the target moved farther away from the system until it's no longer visible on the Range-Doppler plot. The test is first performed with a highly reflective target and, after that, with a human target.

Figure 21 Metallic target at 4.32m

Figure 22 Human target moving farther and closer to the system

With a highly reflective target the maximum distance tested was 4.32 m, the largest distance possible where the system is located. At that distance the target is detected clearly, meaning that it would be possible to detect it at larger ranges. To test the maximum distance with a human target a person walked away from the system and then back towards it. Human detection stops being reliable at a distance of around 3m, at that distance the reflected signal can be lower than the background noise depending on the person’s position.

The range resolution is the ability to distinguish two targets that are close to each other. To check this resolution multiple targets are set in front of the system starting at a distance from each other shorter than the expected resolution, then, the targets are gradually separated. The data is analysed to check at what distance they can be distinguished.

Figure 23 Range-Doppler plot with a pillar at 3m and a metallic box at 4.3m

Figure 24 Human target at 1m and metallic box at 1.84m

This was tested in two different ways, the first one was comparing two objects at a distance of more than 1 m from each other, and the second one consisted of two targets near each other. In both cases it’s possible to discern the targets from each other.

If we consider the system’s characteristics the range resolution is 37.5 cm. The main limitation on the range resolution is the bandwidth, as the following equation indicates:

$$R_{res} = \frac{c}{2B} = 37.5cm$$

Another limitation is the sampling frequency of 491.52 MHz, which results in a resolution of 30.5 cm. Range bins, which are segments used to divide the distance measured by the radar system, are 30.5 cm wide due to this sampling frequency. However, the actual resolution is 37.5 cm, determined by the bandwidth. This discrepancy causes the effect seen in the plots, where the targets are primarily located in one range bin but also partially spread into adjacent bins. Considering the test results, it can be determined that although the theoretical resolution 37.5 cm, it can only be achieved under ideal conditions.

Figure 25 Multitarget test setups

The next test is designed to determine if the system is capable of measuring human breathing. The chest movements caused by breathing are too small to be detected using range estimation, but the motion causes phase changes on the signal at the range where the person is located, so the breathing is detected by monitoring phase changes in the received signal.

Figure 26 Breathing test setup

Figure 27 Phase-Slow Time plot

After that, the system undergoes testing for moving targets. For this test a person walks in front of the system, either walking towards or away from the system. The data obtained is then

represented on a Range-Slow Time plot to show at what range the target was detected at each moment during the measurement.

Figure 28 Moving target setup

Figure 29 Range-Slow Time plot

The last test consists in placing different targets in front of the system to check how much of the signal they reflect back to the system. The results from this test provide information about the kind of targets the system can detect and the maximum range at which they can be detected. The system had already been tested with human targets, metal and concrete, so for this test an additional target made of wood was used.

Figure 30 Wooden target at 1m

05. Platform validation - Sensing and Communications

In the final stage, a test has been developed that integrates both the sensing part and the communication part. The objective of this test is to verify that both parts operate together, complying with the established requirements.

The integrated system allows the representation of the results derived from data communication and sensing, as shown in the previous sections. These indicators are essential to evaluate the overall performance of the system, ensuring that both the data transmission and reception process, as well as the sensing tasks, are executed with the expected accuracy.

Finally, to validate the firmware, both the analysis of the resources used after implementation and the timing analysis were carried out. The Vivado report was used to perform these analyses. The results shown correspond to the project that integrates the four data flows, with the exception of the LDPC block, as mentioned in section 3.

In addition, in order to validate the complete communications system, a Bit Error Rate (BER) measurement is performed. For this measurement, the LDPC block is integrated.

5.1 FPGA analysis

The resource analysis, summarized in Figure 31, shows that there is no resource issue. The highest percentage is allocated to memory resources (BRAM), mainly due to the implementation of an ILA (integrated Logic Analyzer) to analyse one of the frames in real time. The design was optimized to reduce the consumption of both LUTs and BRAMs. This was achieved by using fixed-point blocks, which reduced the number of complex operations requiring DSP and memory. This optimization was fundamental to minimize the use of resources.

Figure 31: Resource analysis.

On the other hand, timing analysis is crucial to verify compliance with signal propagation requirements and ensure correct system operation at the desired clock frequency. As shown in Figure 32, no timing constraint violations were detected, verifying that the system operates correctly in hardware.

Design Timing Summary

Setup	Hold	Pulse Width
Worst Negative Slack (WNS): 0.059 ns	Worst Hold Slack (WHS): 0.003 ns	Worst Pulse Width Slack (WPWS): 1.085 ns
Total Negative Slack (TNS): 0.000 ns	Total Hold Slack (THS): 0.000 ns	Total Pulse Width Negative Slack (TPWS): 0.000 ns
Number of Failing Endpoints: 0	Number of Failing Endpoints: 0	Number of Failing Endpoints: 0
Total Number of Endpoints: 498316	Total Number of Endpoints: 498300	Total Number of Endpoints: 204391

All user specified timing constraints are met.

Figure 32: Timing analysis

5.2 BER measurement

BER (Bite Error Rate) provides a measure of the link quality defined as the rate between erroneous bits and total transmitted bits. To perform this measurement, a block is integrated in the FPGA that, on the one hand, adds and accumulates the bits with errors (comparing the output bits of the LDPC decoder and the transmitted bits) and on the other hand, counts the total received bits. Both parameters are used in MATLAB to calculate the difference between the number of bits with errors and the number of total bits. Figure 33 shows a simplified diagram of the blocks involved in this measure.

Figure 33: Simplified diagram of the blocks involved in the BER calculation

In the validation of this block, tests were performed by varying the distance between the transmitter and the receiver. It should be noted that this parameter is measured independently for the four received signal streams, so that to give a signal BER value, the four values are averaged.

To ensure a representative measurement, the values are recorded when the total bit counter reaches its maximum value. Under these conditions the BER measurements at the different distances are as follows:

- Transmitter to receiver distance of 60 cm: BER = 0.105
- Transmitter to receiver distance of 40 cm: BER = 0.021
- Transmitter to receiver distance of 35 cm: BER = $3.25 \cdot 10^{-4}$

Table 5 shows the BER values for each of the 400 MHz bands at the different distances between transmitter and receiver. The analysis indicates that the fourth band exhibits the poorest performance among the evaluated bands. This observation aligns with the findings presented in Figure 14 and Figure 18, which illustrate the degradation of both constellation and Modulation Error Ratio (MER) in comparison to the other bands. This phenomenon may be attributed to increased losses in the sub-THz channel, as the fourth band operates at the highest carrier frequency ($f_c = 2.2$ GHz).

400 MHz stream/Distance	60 cm	40 cm	35 cm
B1 (f_c 0.85 GHz)	$2.30 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.7578 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.1564 \cdot 10^{-10}$

B2 (f _c 1.30 GHz)	0.0120	6.4662*10 ⁻⁶	3.3052*10 ⁻¹⁰
B3 (f _c 1.75 GHz)	5.992*10 ⁻⁴	3.935*10 ⁻¹⁰	0
B4 (f _c 2.20 GHz)	0.4046	0.0831	1.30*10 ⁻³

Table 5: BER results in the four 400 MHz bands measured at different distances

Conclusions and future work

The design and development of the sub-THz link prototype is part of the 6G-OPENVERSO-NET project under the agreement **6GOPENVERSO-SP1-L1-P3: Aplicaciones de tecnologías 6G sub-THz/THz para futuros servicios XR (Applications of 6G sub-THz/THz technologies to support future XR services)**. The link has been satisfactorily designed and implemented and has been validated through extensive tests according to the test plan define in this document. With the exception of the range resolution, whose achievement would have compromised other key system parameters, the other KPIs have been successfully tested and measured. Notably, we have also assessed the system performance in terms of BER as an additional quality measure of the complete system and it exhibits a satisfactory value. This work package has also explored theoretical approaches to enable NLOS THz communications (see D3.2), namely RIS (Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces) structures are the most promising technique, MIMO systems with very-large arrays and ultra-dense networks UDN). The most promising options is RIS deployment, according to the volume of ongoing research and testbeds, possibly because the introduction of ultra-massive MIMO systems and UDNs implies a profound change in legacy networks, while the integration of RIS is much more straightforward. Also in D3.2, we have investigated the utilization of beamforming techniques for ISAC/XR.

A necessary observation in relation to this project is that the power levels configured in the sub-THz band do not reach the maximum capabilities of the up/down conversion equipment. This limitation is due to a conservative configuration to avoid potential damage of the electronic components, given the high cost of the equipment and the long delivery time to replace or fixing. Besides, the experimental nature of the demonstrator and the characteristics of the waveform, which has a high peak-to-average power ratio (PAPR), strongly recommends setting a low power level. Consequently, a backoff of at least 10 dB of the upconverter compression power has been implemented. This conservative strategy results in a lower power transmission than the maximum power without compromising signal quality. As a result, the performance metrics obtained in the upper bands may not reflect optimal values. Then, maximizing the utilization of the power range provided by the equipment would facilitate improved results.

In summary, this sub-THz link prototype can be understood as a first step towards future utilization in XR applications and scenarios, given the sensing and communication features shown in this deliverable. Therefore, its evolution can involve several steps to have a full, operative sub-THz link:

- Provide the link with bidirectionality.
- Design and implement upper layers to allow IP connectivity.
- Investigate techniques to enhance coverage.